

Quantum Perturbation Theory and the Correspondence Principle

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In (1), standard quantum perturbation theory is developed using $V_0(x)+bV(x)$, $W(x)=W_0(x)+bn_1(x)+b^*bn_2(x)+\dots$ and $E=E_0+E_1b+b^*bE_2+\dots$ where b is small. These values are inserted into the time-independent Schrodinger equation and terms with like order of b collected. Multiplying by W_0 and integrating over x yields an expression for E_i . Multiplying by $W_k(x)$ and integrating yields a projection of $\langle n_i | k \rangle$ where W_k is the k th eigenfunction of $-1/2m d/dx d/dx + V_0(x)$. The projection $\langle n_i | W_0 \rangle$ is determined using $\langle W | W \rangle = 1$ and retaining terms of b to the power i . Thus, many terms are dropped from $\langle W | W \rangle$ and the approach used in (1) is a little tedious as noted in that reference.

In this note, we consider $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$ which yields: $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W_1 + d/dx W_1 d/dx W_0 / W_0 + b V(x) W_1(x) = (E-E_0) W_1(x)$ when inserted into the Schrodinger equation. The same $\langle n_i | W_k \rangle$ projection results, as expected. For $\langle n_i | W_0 \rangle$, however, we argue that $\langle W_0 W_1 | W_0 W_1 \rangle = 1$ leads to a more direct and less tedious equation for evaluating this projection.

We interpret the results which are based on eigenfunctions of H_0 i.e. the Hamiltonian with $bV(x)$ dropped. Finally, we compare the high energy quantum perturbed density with the classical (correspondence) principle i.e density = $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. In the high energy classical limit, matters are not so simple because an expansion of the spatial density in positive powers of b is only valid away from the classical turning points. Near the turning points, a different power series in b holds and technically there is a region for which there is no power series as $E-V_0$ and $b(E_1-V)$ are very similar in value.

Standard Perturbation Theory

$$(H_0 + bV(x)) (W_0 + bn_1(x) + b^*bn_2(x) + b^*b^*bn_3(x) + \dots) = (E_0 + bE_1 + b^*bE_2 + b^*b^*bE_3 + \dots) (W_0 + bn_1(x) + b^*bn_2(x) + b^*b^*bn_3(x) + \dots) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } H_0 = -1/2m d/dx d/dx + V_0(x)$$

Coefficients related to a particular order of b starting with 1 are collected and then one continues to 2 etc. Next, multiplying by $|W_0\rangle$ yields E_i and by $|W_k\rangle$, $\langle n_i | W_k \rangle$ for k not equal to 0. Here W_0 is not the ground state, but the state being examined. The function $n_{(i-1)}$ is associated with $bV(x)$ to obtain b to the power of i .

This leaves the case of the projection $\langle n_i | W_0 \rangle$ which may be obtained from the normalization condition:

$$\langle (W_0 + bn_1(x) + b^*bn_2(x) + b^*b^*bn_3(x) + \dots) | (W_0 + bn_1(x) + b^*bn_2(x) + b^*b^*bn_3(x) + \dots) \rangle = 1 \quad ((2))$$

Considering b to the i th power in ((2)), one retains b to the i th power both in the bra and ket and expands. Many terms are of higher order than b to the i and are dropped. As noted in (1), this is somewhat tedious.

$$\text{For } i=1: \quad H_0 n_1(x) + V(x) W_0 = E_0 n_1 + E_1 W_0$$

Multiplying by W_0 and integrating over dx yields: $\langle W_0|V|W_0\rangle = E_1$. Multiplying by W_k and integrating over dx yields: $(E_k - E_0) \langle n_1|W_k\rangle + \langle W_0|V|W_k\rangle = 0$. Thus, one only needs $\langle n_1|W_0\rangle$ which follows from: ((2)) i.e. $\langle n_1|W_0\rangle + \langle W_0|n_1\rangle = 0$. For higher values of i , it is not zero.

Product Wavefunctions $W(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$

It is possible to use product wavefunctions where $W_0(x)$ is a solution of H_0 i.e. with $bV(x)$, the perturbative potential, dropped. Then:

$$W_1(x) = (1 + b n_1/W_0 + b^*b n_2/W_0 + b^*b^*b n_3/W_0 + \dots) \quad ((3)) \text{ where}$$

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1 - 1/m \frac{dW_1}{dx} \frac{dW_0}{dx} / W_0 + bV(x) W_1 = (bE_1 + b^*bE_2 + b^*b^*bE_3 + \dots) W_1 \quad ((4))$$

One may readily obtain E_i by multiplying by $W_0^*W_0$ and integrating over x by using integration by parts on the first term of the LHS of ((4)). The first two terms on the LHS always cancel. For b to the first power: $W_0W_0 V(x) = W_0W_0 E_1$ as above.

To obtain $\langle n_i|W_k\rangle$, multiply ((4)) by $W_0 W_k$ and integrate the first term on the LHS of ((4)) twice by parts and the second term once by parts. Next use $H_0W_k = E_kW_k$ and $H_0W_0 = E_0W_0$. Thus, the first two terms on the LHS of ((4)) always yield:

$$(E_0 - E_k) W_0W_k n_i/W_0 = (E_0 - E_k) \langle n_i|W_k\rangle \text{ where one is interested in the term of } b \text{ to the } i\text{th power.}$$

Thus, the product wavefunction approach yields the same expressions for E_i and $\langle n_i|W_k\rangle$ as the approach of (1) which is no surprise. Furthermore, the two calculations are equally laborious. There is no ease of calculation obtained from using the product wavefunction for these two calculations so far.

We argue, however, that it is simpler to find $\langle n_i|W_0\rangle$ using the product wavefunction approach.

$$\text{Let } W_1 = (1 + f(x)/W_0) \quad ((5)) \text{ where } f(x) = b n_1(x) + b^*b n_2(x) + b^*b^*b n_3(x) + \dots$$

Then:

$$1 = \langle W|W\rangle = \text{Integral } dx \quad W_0W_0 (1 + f^*f / (W_0W_0) + 2f/W_0) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\text{Integral } dx [f^*f + 2f W_0] = 0 \quad ((6))$$

One may begin with $i=1$ and proceed to $i=2$ etc. For $i=1$ $\langle n_1|W_0\rangle = 0$ because the lowest order of f is b . For a particular i , one simply uses n_i in the second term and all products yielding

b to the i th power in the first term. The coefficient is either 1 or 2. All lower order i values have already been integrated to 0.

Thus, for $i=2$ $\langle n_1 | n_1 \rangle + 2 \langle n_2 | W_0 \rangle = 0$ as in (1).

We think the form of ((6)) is simpler than using ((2)). Of course, ((6)) could have been developed using the standard perturbation form, a product wavefunction approach is not needed, but it seems to follow more naturally in such an approach.

Interpretation of Perturbation Theory

If one considers the first order correction term to $W(x)$, namely $\sum_{k \neq 0} \langle W_0 | V | W_k \rangle W_k / (E_0 - E_k)$, one may observe it contains W_k states i.e. different energy levels than W_0 . The perturbation potential $bV(x)$, however, is very small. According to arguments we made in previous notes, $V_0(x)$ is stochastic i.e. $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ so it may still render large momentum hits even though on average the force is very small. $V(x)$, the perturbative potential, however, renders similar stochastic hits. We have argued there exists a momentum distribution at each x i.e. $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. This includes momenta with values of $p^2/2m \gg E$, so there is a probability for very large single particle momenta as well as tunneling to occur. E is only an average. Adding $bV(x)$ may change the distribution slightly, but from the point of view of someone familiar with the states of H_0 , such a change must be due to a mixture W_k ($k \neq 0$). W_k , however, is an ensemble: $\sum_p b(p) \exp(ipx)$. These different p values occur at different times. Thus, a mixture of W_k 's which add and cancel simply means one may observe different $a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ values at each x . It seems one does not have to take the W_k 's as representing alternate states existing in a small range of time. There is a whole mixture of different W_k pieces existing during all time ranges. $P(p/x)$ already is a probability representation of a stochastic complicated particle motion. The W_k 's are convenient mathematically because their properties are well known. One, it seems, should be careful about making conclusions from limited probabilities. For example, one may toss a coin five times and receive all heads and thus conclude the coin has heads on both sides. Suddenly, five tosses of all tails occur and one may conclude the coin has changed to include tails on both sides. Neither explanation is correct. The coin toss results, however, represent actual states of the coin while $P(p/x)$ is a probability distribution. If the probability distribution changes, one does not have the resonance W_0 any longer.

Thus we argue one should be careful interpreting the physical existence of W_k states, although they are convenient mathematically. It may look for some periods of time as if $P(p/x)$ corresponds to one W_k or another, but like the coin toss, this should change in time as all W_k 's are ultimately part of the first order correction.

Comparison with Classical Density in the High Energy Limit (Correspondence Principle)

In the high energy limit, $C/v(x)$ is the classical density which should somewhat match the peaks (or near to the peaks) of the quantum spatial density $W_0^* W_0$. One may consider $C/v(x)$ with the velocity resulting from the perturbed potential to see the results. First:

$$\int C(b)/v(x,b) dx = \int dx C(b) / \sqrt{E+E1b - Vo-bV} = 1 \quad ((7))$$

Let $C(b) = A + bF1 + b^2F2 + \dots$ where $A = \int dx 1/\sqrt{(2m)(E-V)}$

(Technically, such an expansion does not hold near the turning points of $E-Vo$ as will be seen later. Furthermore, there is a region for which $E-Vo$ is as small as $b(E1-V)$ and it seems one cannot do an expansion in such a region. Thus, using $F1$ and $F2$ is an approximation at best.) Then ((7)) becomes:

$$1 = 1 - bF1 + b^2F2 \text{ to first order.}$$

Thus, the first order integrated correction in b to the density vanishes just as in the quantum case, as expected.

For the second order case:

$$(A+bF1+b^2F2) 1/A [1-bF1-b^2F2/A + 1/(A^2) (bF1+b^2F2)^2 + \dots]$$

$$\text{The second order correction is: } -b^2 F1^2/(A^2) + b^2 F2/(A^2) = 0 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the second order integrated density correction etc is zero just as in the quantum case where the second order spatial density correction is:

$$-b^2 \sum_{k \neq 0} |\langle k|V|0\rangle \langle 0|V|k\rangle| / [(E0-Ek)(E0-Ek)] + b^2 \sum_{k \neq 0} |\langle k|V|0\rangle \langle 0|V|k\rangle| / [(E0-Ek)(E0-Ek)] = 0.$$

Even though the integral of density shows no corrections in the classical case, the density itself differs from $Co/v0(x)$ as shown by ((7)). One may use $1/\sqrt{1+x} = 1+.5x -.25x^2 + \dots$ to expand ((7)), but only in regions away from the classical turning point because very near such turning points $E-Vo(x)$ approaches 0 and the term $E-Vo$ may be smaller than $b(E1-V)$. Technically, there is also a region for which $E-Vo$ and $b(E1-V)$ are of the same order and one cannot really expand at all.

Away from Classical Turning Points:

$$\text{Classical density to second order} = 1/\sqrt{(2m)(E-Vo)} [1+.5b (E1-V)/(E-Vo) -.25b^2 (E1-V)(E1-V)/\{(E-Vo)(E-Vo)\} + \dots] * 1/C(b) \quad \text{where } C(b) = A + bF1 + b^2F2$$

$1/C(b)$ approximate = $(1/A) [1-bF1/A-b^2F2/A + b^2F1^2/(AA) + \dots]$ where $A = \int dx 1/\sqrt{(2m)(E-Vo)}$ This assumes that regions where $E-Vo$ is of the same order as $b(E1-V)$ do not contribute to the normalization and it is not clear that that is the case as the integrand is large there, although this depends on the value of b .

$$F1 = \int dx 1/\sqrt{(2m)} 1/\sqrt{E-Vo} .5b (E1-V)/(E-Vo) \quad \text{and} \quad F2 = \int dx 1/\sqrt{(2m)} 1/\sqrt{E-Vo} -.25b^2 (E1-V)(E1-V)/\{(E-Vo)(E-Vo)\} \quad \text{so:}$$

Classical density to second order = $\frac{1}{\sqrt{(2m)(E-V_0)}} \left\{ 1 - \frac{bF_1}{AA} + \frac{1}{AA} .5b \frac{(E_1-V)}{(E-V_0)} \right.$
 $\left. + \frac{b^2 F_2}{AA} - \frac{b^2 F_1}{AA} .5 \frac{(E_1-V)}{(E-V_0)} + \frac{b^2 F_1^2}{AAA} - .25 \frac{b^2}{A} \right.$
 $\left. \frac{(E_1-V)(E_1-V)}{(E-V_0)(E-V_0) + \dots} \right\} \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{for } x \text{ not near the turning points of } E-V_0(x)$

F1 and F2 are obtained from integrals integrated in a region with a cutoff excluding the turning points. A different series is needed in the region near the turning points, but leads to tiny values which may be arranged to be smaller than b^2 . Technically there is a region for which there is no expansion when $E-V_0$ is similar to $b(E_1-V)$. Thus, F1 and F2 are only approximations. If one is uncomfortable using F1 and F2, they may be set to 0 in ((9a)) and a relative density obtained to second order in b .

Near the turning points where $E-V_0(x)=0$ (or close) a different expression for classical spatial density is needed.

In such a region, the relative density is:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{E-V_0(x) + bE_1 - bV}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{b(E_1-V)}} \left[1 + .5 \frac{(E-V_0)}{b(E_1-V)} - .25 \frac{(E-V_0)(E-V_0)}{bb} \right. \\ \left. \frac{(E_1-V)(E_1-V) + \dots}{(E_1-V)(E_1-V) + \dots} \right] \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{because } b(E_1-V) \gg E-V_0 \quad ((9b))$$

It is not an expansion in positive powers of b . It should be noted that in ((9b)) $\frac{(E-V_0)(E-V_0)}{bb} \ll 1$ throughout the region for which it holds.

$1/C(b)$, the normalization constant portion in this region, may be expanded in a similar manner.

$$C(b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{b}} G_1(E_1) + b^{-3/2} G_2(E_1, E) + b^{-5/2} G_3(E_1, E) + \dots$$

$$C(b) = b^{-5/2} [G_3(E_1, E) + b G_2 + bb G_1]$$

Given that G_3, G_2 and G_1 are tiny and one has $1/C(b)$ of order greater than b^2 , these values do not really affect F1 and F2 used above. Thus, the overall normalization constant is $\frac{1}{A} (1 + F_1 b + F_2 bb)$ which may be combined with ((9b)), although this is only an approximation and it is not clear how useful it is. There is another region for which $E-V_0$ is of the same order as $b(E_1-V)$ and one cannot expand in this region and may not be able to find a closed form for the integral.

To determine the region itself one needs to apply a cutoff using $b(E_1-V) \gg E-V_0$, where b is a known tiny value, but $E-V_0$ is much smaller.

As an aside, it is interesting to note that $\frac{1}{\sqrt{E-V_0}}$ diverges near the turning point, but its integral does not, at least for the oscillator for which $V_0 = .5kx^2$. If one uses the substitution: $\sqrt{.5kx^2} = \sqrt{E} \sin(a)$, then $\int \frac{dx}{v(x)}$ is proportional to $\int \frac{da \cos(a)}{\cos(a)}$ so there is no divergence.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue one may use the product form $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$ where $W_1(x)=1 + b n_1(x)/W_0(x) + b^2 n_2(x)/W_0(x) + b^3 n_3(x)/W_0(x) + \dots$ together with the equation: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1 - \frac{1}{m} \frac{dW_1}{dx} \frac{dW_0}{dx} / W_0 + b V(x) W_1(x) = (bE_1 + b^2 E_2 + b^3 E_3 + \dots) W_1$ to obtain the same perturbation results for $\langle n_i | W_k \rangle$ and E_i as in standard perturbation theory (1). $\langle n_i | W_0 \rangle$ is obtained from the normalization condition: $\langle W | W \rangle = 1$. We argue using the product wavefunction approach leads to a simpler evaluation of $\langle n_i | W_0 \rangle$ through:

$\int dx (f^* f + 2f W_0)$ where $f = b n_1(x) + b^2 n_2(x) + b^3 n_3(x) + \dots$

Thus, $2f W_0$ yields $2 \langle n_i | W_0 \rangle$ and one need only keep product $f^* f$ terms with b to the i th power terms. These have a coefficient of 1 or 2.

In the high energy limit, we give an expression ((9a)) for the "classical" spatial density to second order in b assuming one is away from the classical turning points. The functions F_1 and F_2 are probably not reliable in expressing the entire normalization constant, so setting $F_1 = F_2 = 0$ in ((9a)) yields a relative spatial density.

Near the turning point a different expression holds as shown in ((9b)) which is not a power series in positive b powers. The contribution to normalization constants from this region seems to be small than b^2 where b is tiny. There is technically a region in between the two with no expansion because $E - V_0$ is of the same order as $b(E_1 - V)$. Such a region could contribute to the normalization constant, thus using F_1 and F_2 only from the region where $E - V_0 \gg b(E_1 - V)$ may not be reliable. Thus, for the high energy "classical" limit, matters are not completely clear, yet by the correspondence principle this should match the high energy limit of the quantum perturbation limit which is still a power series expansion in positive powers of b .

References

1. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Perturbation_theory_\(quantum_mechanics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Perturbation_theory_(quantum_mechanics))